

The ^1H nmr spectra of the ligand show signals at δ 7.1–9.0 due to aromatic protons¹⁰, at δ 2.46 due to methyl protons, and singlet at δ 8.3–8.6 due to $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$ moiety. In the complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} the latter signal undergoes a downward shift at δ 8.8–9.1 indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in the complexes¹¹.

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Stability Constants of Ternary Metal(II)/2,2'-Dipyridylamine/Amino Acidate Complexes of Nickel, Zinc and Cadmium

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THE present paper reports the stability constants of ternary MAL complexes, where, $\text{M}=\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ; $\text{A}=2,2'$ -dipyridylamine and $\text{L}=\text{anion}$

of glycine, α -alanine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, serine, threonine, methionine and aspartic acid determined by modified pH metric method following Irving–Rossotti pH-titration technique^{1,2}.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A. R. grade. Solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in conductivity water. Free perchloric acid and metal perchlorate solutions were standardised by acid-base³ and complexometric⁴ methods. The experimental set-up and calculations were employed as described by Mavani *et al.*⁵. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 M using 1 M sodium perchlorate. A Elico LI-10 T pH meter was employed for pH measurements. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 27° using 0.2 M NaOH.

The formation constants were calculated by the literature methods⁶. Precise values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ (Table 1) were determined by the method of averages⁶, here L stands for amino acid anions.

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ values are found to be much higher than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{ML}}$, and are only slightly lower than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$. The order of formation constants for the mixed ligand chelates is the same as that for the binary ML complexes⁷. The $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ values are in the order, glycine $\gg$ α -alanine $\approx$ leucine $\gg$ isoleucine $>$ valine, serine $\approx$ threonine $\approx$ methionine $<$ aspartic acid for the ligands L. The sequence may be explained⁷ in terms of the basicities and structures of the secondary ligands L. Higher values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ originate from the π -acidic nature of 2,2'-dipyridylamine, besides the $\text{N} \rightarrow \text{M}(\text{II})$ σ -bonding, there exists strong $\text{M}(\text{II}) \rightarrow \text{N}$ π -interaction. As a result the electronegativity of the $\text{M}(\text{II})$ ion in $[\text{M}(2,2'\text{-dipyridylamine})]^{2+}$ complex is not significantly different than that of $[\text{M}(\text{aq})_n]^{2+}$ ion^{8,9}.

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF METAL(II)/2,2'-DIPYRIDYLAMINE AMINO ACIDATE COMPLEXES

Amino acid ligand	Temp. = 27°, Ionic strength = 0.2 M (NaClO_4)								
	$\log K_{\text{NIL}}^{\text{NI}}$	$\log K_{\text{NIL}_2}^{\text{NIL}}$	$\log K_{\text{NIAL}}^{\text{NIA}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnL}}^{\text{Zn}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnL}_2}^{\text{ZnL}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnAL}}^{\text{ZnA}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdL}}^{\text{Cd}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdL}_2}^{\text{CdL}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdAL}}^{\text{CdA}}$
Glycine	5.90	5.05	5.23	5.22	4.37	5.08	4.24	3.69	4.20
α -Alanine	5.55	4.53	4.93	5.17	4.10	4.92	4.27	3.46	4.15
Leucine	5.54	4.55	5.24	4.74	4.36	4.69	4.92	3.56	4.18
Isoleucine	5.43	4.49	4.95	4.88	4.33	4.81	3.91	3.37	3.96
Valine	5.48	4.42	4.90	4.74	4.24	4.63	3.91	3.22	3.88
Serine	5.69	4.76	5.21	5.06	4.11	4.71	3.95	3.30	3.76
Threonine	5.96	4.93	5.35	5.16	4.19	4.85	4.02	3.20	3.72
Methionine	5.60	4.81	5.38	4.69	3.96	4.54	4.30	4.04	3.85
Aspartic acid	7.12	5.32	6.75	5.74	4.09	5.52	4.53	3.50	4.61

* Limits of error: $\pm 0.01 - 0.08$ in log scales.

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Ligand Exchange Equilibria of Metal Complexes. Part-II. Extraction and Exchange Constants of Metal- α -benzoin Oximates in Chloroform†

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METAL chelates extracted by organic solvents can be converted into other metal chelates by the addition of a suitable chelating agent². Metal diphenylcarbazone in solution reacts with α -benzoin oxime liberating free diphenylcarbazone and form metal- α -benzoin oximate.

The equilibrium constant is related to the extraction constant of the metal chelate. Using the extraction constant, the equilibrium constant of an exchange can be calculated and vice versa.

Experimental

Diphenylcarbazones : Metal-diphenylcarbazones were prepared³ by shaking 1.0×10^{-3} M diphenylcarbazone (H_2Dp) in chloroform with excess aqueous metal salt solutions at desired pH values.

α -Benzoin oximates : Solid complexes of Ag, Tl^I, Cd, Zn, Cu, Ni and Co were prepared by refluxing α -benzoin oxime (HBo) and the metal salts in ethanolic solution. Solutions of 1.0×10^{-3} M metal- α -benzoin oximates were prepared in chloroform.

Thallium diphenylcarbazone, Tl(HDp), was prepared by shaking excess of aqueous solution of thallium(I) chloride at pH 7.0 with chloroform solution (1.0×10^{-3} M) of diphenylcarbazone.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of red coloured thallium diphenylcarbazone solution in chloroform shows a single strong band at 540 nm ($\epsilon = 3740 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). When a chloroform solution of α -benzoin oxime is added to thallium diphenylcarbazone, α -benzoin oxime displaces diphenylcarbazone and equilibrium is reached within a few minutes. At equilibrium, the colour of the Tl(HDp) solution changes from red to faint pink,

for which the equilibrium constant,

$$E_{Tl(HDp)-HBo}^{org} = \frac{[Tl(Bo)]_{org}[H_2Dp]_{org}}{[Tl(HDp)]_{org}[HBo]_{org}}$$

The reversibility of the reaction is confirmed by mixing thallium- α -benzoin oximate with diphenylcarbazone. Similar procedure was adopted for confirming the reversibility of all the reactions studied in this work,

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITION EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF EXCHANGE REACTION (E), AND EXTRACTION CONSTANTS OF METAL-DITHIZONATES ($KM(HDz)_n$), METAL- α -BENZOIN OXIMATES, ($KM(Bo)_n$) AND METAL-DIPHENYLCARBAZONATES ($K(HDp)_n$) IN CHLOROFORM

Reaction	pH	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon_{\lambda_{max}}$	log E (± 0.1)	log $KM(HDz)_n^*$	log $KM(Bo)_n$	log $KM(HDp)_n$
Tl(HDp) + HBo = Tl(Bo) + H ₂ Dp	7.0	540	8 740	-1.8	-3.80	-5.89	-4.09
Cd(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Cd(Bo) ₂ + H ₂ Dp	8.0	550	12 200	-2.5	0.50	-4.36	-1.88
Zn(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Zn(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	540	9 920	-2.3	1.0	-2.90	-0.63
Cu(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Cu(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.5	550	31 600	-2.4	8.70	2.20	4.57
Ni(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Ni(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	550	25 800	-1.1	2.46	-6.04	-4.97
Co(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Co(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	7.0	550	23 200	-1.7	-1.50	-7.98	-6.32
Pd(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Pd(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	2.3	570	3 200	-2.3	>27.0	>16.40	>18.68
Pb(HDp) ₂ + 2HBo = Pb(Bo) ₂ + 2H ₂ Dp	6.0	550	5 200	-2.3	-0.90	-7.85	-5.52

* Lit. value.

† Part-I, Ref. 1.